

BMI and contraceptives affect new age-, sex-, and puberty-adjusted IGF-I and IGFBP-3 reference ranges across life span

Supplemental Text

Assay comparison for IGF-I and IGFBP-3 between the ECLIA and the CLIA assay

Methods: For 3476 samples from 2050 subjects without intake of CD or HRT from the LIFE Child study and from the student cohort (mean age $10.7 \pm$ SD: 5.6 years, range: 0.2 to 40.6 years), IGF-I and IGFBP-3 values were analyzed using both the ECLIA and the CLIA assay (Suppl. Table 6).

Results: The results showed good overall agreement for IGF-I (concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) = 0.980 (95% CI: 0.979 to 0.981), slope = 0.98 (Suppl. Figure 1) but indicated somewhat lower values for the ECLIA vs. the CLIA assay. The agreement for IGFBP-3 was slightly weaker, likewise with lower values for ECLIA vs. CLIA (CCC = 0.802 (95% CI: 0.791 to 0.813), slope = 1.08 among values lower than 9200 ng/mL (Suppl. Figure 1). These findings suggest a moderate level of agreement in the absolute values of both proteins, with a mean difference of 4.3% for IGF-I and 10.8% for IGFBP-3 (Suppl. Table 6). The mean difference using the SDS values was also moderate with 0.14 SDS for IGF-I SDS and with -0.37 for IGFBP-3 SDS. Accordingly, approximately 18% of all measured samples for IGF-I and 22% for IGFBP-3 would reveal different findings at relevant diagnostic differences of more than one SDS (Suppl. Table 7).

Discussion: Measuring IGF-I and IGFBP-3 on the ECLIA and the CLIA assay using the same reference preparation for calibration should deliver largely comparable results. This hypothesis was confirmed by a high degree of correlation for IGF-I but only a moderate one for IGFBP-3. Overall, the ECLIA measured slightly lower IGF-I and IGFBP-3 levels than the CLIA assay among values lower than 9200 ng/mL (Suppl. Figure 1). The differences may be mainly explained by different antigen epitope recognition of the respective antibodies. When the effect of a different reference cohort for the CLIA-SDS values was additionally considered, we uncovered a not negligible shift of >1 SDS between both methods, with putative consequences on diagnostic decisions. Accordingly, IGF-I and IGFBP-3 results from the ECLIA and the CLIA assay cannot be interchanged.

Supplemental Figures and Tables

Suppl. Figure 1: Comparison of IGF-I and IGFBP-3 levels measured by the ECLIA and the CLIA assay using the same calibrator in 3476 samples from 2050 subjects (grey dots): Passing-Bablok regression reflects a thick solid regression line, the $line\ y = x$ reflects a dashed line. The concordance correlation coefficients CCCs for IGF-I and IGFBP-3 were 0.980 and 0.802, respectively.

Suppl. Figure 2: The 2.5th, 50th, and 97.5th percentiles of the age- and sex-adjusted reference percentiles for IGF-I and IGFBP-3 measured by the ECLIA assay (children and adolescents <19 years and BMI $\pm$ 1.881 SDS, adults $\geq$ 19 years and BMI >18 to 30 kg/m²). Percentiles were calculated for males, for females without (w/o) CD or HRT intake, as well as for females both with (w) and without (w/o) CD or HRT intake.

Suppl. Figure 3: IGF-I (A) and IGFBP-3 (B) values of adolescent and adult female samples with CD or HRT medication (14 to 76 years) compared to the reference cohort. The number of subjects and the number of samples for participants with multiple visits (in parentheses) are shown. For adolescents and adults, samples with estrogen- and progestin-based components of contraceptive drugs (epCDs) are presented. For adolescents, samples of subjects with non-reported CD use with SHBG $\geq$ 200 ng/mL and for adults, samples with progestin-based contraceptives drugs (pCDs) and hormone replacement therapy (HRT) are labeled.

Suppl. Figure 4: Mean IGF-I (A) and IGFBP-3 (B) levels of the reference cohort are shown depending on pubertal stage: Data from females taking and not taking CDs in TS 4 and TS 5 were compared with each other and with males as well. The results were derived from generalized additive models for location, scale, and shape. The 95% confidence intervals (CI) are represented by vertical lines.

Suppl. Table 1: Quality control (QC) data for all runs in the measurements of hormone levels to calculate reference ranges: Mean IGF-I and IGFBP-3 data from the ECLIA (cobas® e 601 assay).

Parameter	N	Mean level	Min	Max	CV [%]	Mean Recovery [%]
IGF-I [ng/mL]	404	54.6	51.2	58.3	2.3	96.7
	404	320	301	342	2.4	95.8
	24	56.9	53.1	60.6	3.9	98.9
	24	332	303	366	5.1	96.0
	8	56.9	55.1	346	1.9	101.7
	8	337	328	346	2.5	101.3
IGFBP-3 [ng/mL]	314	744	661	853	4.8	101.4
	318	6632	5919	7895	5.1	100.7
	160	995	840	1140	5.4	101.6
	160	6412	5730	7060	4.9	103.4
	16	732	708	761	1.9	99.2
	16	6609	6317	7047	3.1	99.9

Suppl. Table 2: Age-dependent percentiles of IGF-I (ng/mL) for children, adolescents, and adults (n = number of samples). (A) Males, (B) Females who were not taking CDs or HRT, (C) Females who were taking or not taking CDs or HRT

2A: Males

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0 th Perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
0.25	75	14.07	40.05	83.16	40.05	0.43	0.41	1.91
0.5	110	14.28	40.48	83.87	40.48	0.43	0.41	1.92
0.75	35	14.56	41.07	84.87	41.07	0.43	0.41	1.94
1	74	14.93	41.83	86.18	41.83	0.43	0.41	1.97
1.5	27	15.94	43.95	89.88	43.95	0.42	0.41	2.02
2	43	17.45	47.15	95.54	47.15	0.42	0.41	2.09
2.5	56	19.63	51.77	103.80	51.77	0.41	0.40	2.17
3	50	22.56	57.84	114.62	57.84	0.41	0.40	2.25
3.5	55	26.16	64.98	127.13	64.98	0.40	0.39	2.33
4	53	30.20	72.51	139.89	72.51	0.39	0.38	2.40
4.5	49	34.31	79.43	150.78	79.43	0.38	0.37	2.47
5	57	38.30	85.25	158.75	85.25	0.37	0.36	2.51
5.5	52	42.52	90.65	165.08	90.65	0.35	0.35	2.52
6	65	47.49	96.76	172.04	96.76	0.33	0.33	2.50
6.5	62	53.62	104.55	181.78	104.55	0.32	0.31	2.45
7	66	59.54	111.65	190.72	111.65	0.30	0.28	2.37
7.5	58	63.66	115.68	195.54	115.68	0.29	0.23	2.28
8	77	67.28	119.47	201.35	119.47	0.28	0.17	2.18
8.5	85	70.96	124.10	209.82	124.10	0.28	0.12	2.09
9	79	74.62	129.33	220.21	129.33	0.28	0.06	2.04
9.5	81	78.85	136.16	233.96	136.16	0.28	0.02	2.01
10	76	83.68	145.3	253.23	145.30	0.28	-0.01	2.01
10.5	88	88.50	157.39	281.76	157.39	0.30	-0.02	2.03
11	69	92.15	172.48	322.81	172.48	0.32	0.00	2.07
11.5	75	93.98	189.26	371.79	189.26	0.35	0.05	2.11
12	77	97.55	210.99	423.45	210.99	0.38	0.14	2.15
12.5	74	109.08	244.92	479.35	244.92	0.38	0.25	2.16
13	65	130.62	288.46	530.54	288.46	0.35	0.38	2.12
13.5	66	158.73	328.43	560.06	328.43	0.31	0.49	2.02
14	66	187.96	354.97	562.81	354.97	0.27	0.59	1.87
14.5	73	201.12	357.61	526.78	357.61	0.24	0.83	2.28
15	59	209.01	357.70	522.05	357.70	0.23	0.78	2.26
15.5	49	211.96	352.96	511.94	352.96	0.22	0.72	2.23
16	54	210.27	343.61	496.67	343.61	0.22	0.67	2.21
16.5	23	205.06	330.88	477.75	330.88	0.21	0.63	2.19
17	27	197.62	316.30	456.99	316.30	0.21	0.59	2.16
17.5	15	189.00	301.06	435.83	301.06	0.21	0.55	2.14
18	12	179.97	286.02	415.31	286.02	0.21	0.52	2.11
18.5	13	171.09	271.80	396.16	271.80	0.21	0.49	2.08
19	5	162.75	258.83	378.87	258.83	0.21	0.47	2.05
19.5	2	155.27	247.41	363.83	247.41	0.22	0.45	2.03

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0 th Perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
20	4	148.81	237.72	351.22	237.72	0.22	0.43	2.00
20.5	20	143.44	229.78	341.05	229.78	0.22	0.41	1.97
21	35	139.07	223.41	333.04	223.41	0.22	0.39	1.94
21.5	24	135.54	218.34	326.81	218.34	0.22	0.38	1.91
22	30	132.72	214.34	322.01	214.34	0.22	0.37	1.88
22.5	9	130.43	211.13	318.24	211.13	0.22	0.36	1.86
23	17	128.45	208.34	314.94	208.34	0.22	0.35	1.83
23.5	8	126.51	205.58	311.58	205.58	0.23	0.34	1.81
24	21	124.43	202.54	307.69	202.54	0.23	0.34	1.78
24.5	8	122.06	198.98	302.92	198.98	0.23	0.33	1.76
25	18	119.41	194.95	297.36	194.95	0.23	0.33	1.73
25.5	13	116.70	190.80	291.52	190.80	0.23	0.32	1.71
26	17	114.14	186.85	285.92	186.85	0.23	0.32	1.69
26.5	11	111.86	183.36	280.96	183.36	0.23	0.32	1.67
27	12	110.02	180.53	276.95	180.53	0.23	0.32	1.65
27.5	9	108.61	178.40	273.94	178.40	0.23	0.32	1.63
28	23	107.56	176.83	271.73	176.83	0.23	0.32	1.61
28.5	11	106.81	175.70	270.11	175.70	0.23	0.32	1.59
29	17	106.28	174.90	268.90	174.90	0.23	0.32	1.57
29.5	18	105.92	174.32	267.96	174.32	0.23	0.32	1.56
30	14	105.67	173.87	267.12	173.87	0.23	0.32	1.54
30.5	14	105.47	173.46	266.27	173.46	0.23	0.32	1.53
31	13	105.28	173.02	265.31	173.02	0.23	0.33	1.52
31.5	11	105.04	172.49	264.16	172.49	0.23	0.33	1.51
32	8	104.72	171.81	262.75	171.81	0.22	0.33	1.50
32.5	7	104.29	170.94	261.02	170.94	0.22	0.34	1.49
33	10	103.73	169.87	258.98	169.87	0.22	0.34	1.48
33.5	4	103.07	168.65	256.72	168.65	0.22	0.35	1.47
34	12	102.33	167.32	254.30	167.32	0.22	0.35	1.47
34.5	5	101.51	165.90	251.79	165.90	0.22	0.36	1.46
35	7	100.63	164.44	249.25	164.44	0.22	0.37	1.46
35.5	5	99.72	162.96	246.73	162.96	0.22	0.37	1.46
36	11	98.78	161.49	244.28	161.49	0.22	0.38	1.46
36.5	6	97.81	160.04	241.90	160.04	0.22	0.39	1.46
37	7	96.83	158.61	239.60	158.61	0.22	0.40	1.46
37.5	6	95.84	157.20	237.40	157.20	0.22	0.40	1.46
38	17	94.84	155.84	235.30	155.84	0.22	0.41	1.47
38.5	3	93.84	154.51	233.30	154.51	0.22	0.42	1.47
39	13	92.85	153.22	231.40	153.22	0.22	0.43	1.48
39.5	5	91.86	151.98	229.61	151.98	0.22	0.44	1.48
40	3	90.89	150.79	227.91	150.79	0.22	0.44	1.49
40.5	4	89.95	149.65	226.30	149.65	0.22	0.45	1.50
41	34	89.04	148.55	224.78	148.55	0.22	0.46	1.50
41.5	38	88.17	147.51	223.33	147.51	0.23	0.47	1.51
42	48	87.35	146.52	221.96	146.52	0.23	0.47	1.52
42.5	35	86.59	145.58	220.67	145.58	0.23	0.48	1.53
43	46	85.88	144.7	219.44	144.70	0.23	0.48	1.54
43.5	37	85.23	143.87	218.29	143.87	0.23	0.49	1.55

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0 th Perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
44	56	84.63	143.10	217.22	143.10	0.23	0.49	1.56
44.5	47	84.07	142.37	216.21	142.37	0.23	0.49	1.57
45	52	83.55	141.68	215.28	141.68	0.23	0.49	1.58
45.5	37	83.06	141.04	214.43	141.04	0.23	0.50	1.59
46	31	82.60	140.43	213.65	140.43	0.23	0.50	1.60
46.5	46	82.16	139.86	212.94	139.86	0.23	0.50	1.61
47	46	81.74	139.30	212.29	139.30	0.23	0.50	1.62
47.5	36	81.31	138.75	211.68	138.75	0.23	0.49	1.63
48	43	80.88	138.20	211.08	138.20	0.23	0.49	1.64
48.5	32	80.42	137.61	210.47	137.61	0.23	0.49	1.65
49	36	79.94	137.00	209.82	137.00	0.24	0.49	1.65
49.5	45	79.42	136.33	209.13	136.33	0.24	0.48	1.66
50	38	78.85	135.59	208.36	135.59	0.24	0.48	1.67
50.5	43	78.23	134.79	207.50	134.79	0.24	0.48	1.67
51	41	77.56	133.92	206.55	133.92	0.24	0.47	1.68
51.5	24	76.85	132.98	205.51	132.98	0.24	0.47	1.68
52	21	76.11	131.98	204.39	131.98	0.24	0.47	1.68
52.5	37	75.34	130.95	203.23	130.95	0.24	0.46	1.69
53	21	74.56	129.89	202.02	129.89	0.24	0.46	1.69
53.5	32	73.79	128.83	200.81	128.83	0.25	0.46	1.69
54	29	73.02	127.78	199.59	127.78	0.25	0.45	1.69
54.5	21	72.28	126.74	198.40	126.74	0.25	0.45	1.69
55	20	71.58	125.74	197.24	125.74	0.25	0.44	1.70
55.5	22	70.91	124.78	196.14	124.78	0.25	0.44	1.70
56	26	70.28	123.88	195.12	123.88	0.25	0.44	1.70
56.5	22	69.71	123.05	194.19	123.05	0.25	0.43	1.70
57	17	69.20	122.29	193.38	122.29	0.25	0.42	1.70
57.5	20	68.74	121.62	192.68	121.62	0.25	0.42	1.70
58	26	68.33	121.03	192.11	121.03	0.25	0.41	1.70
58.5	28	67.99	120.53	191.67	120.53	0.26	0.41	1.70
59	18	67.70	120.12	191.38	120.12	0.26	0.40	1.70
59.5	29	67.47	119.79	191.22	119.79	0.26	0.39	1.70
60	19	67.29	119.55	191.20	119.55	0.26	0.39	1.70
60.5	20	67.15	119.38	191.30	119.38	0.26	0.38	1.70
61	26	67.05	119.27	191.50	119.27	0.26	0.37	1.70
61.5	24	66.98	119.20	191.79	119.20	0.26	0.37	1.70
62	19	66.92	119.18	192.16	119.18	0.26	0.36	1.70
62.5	31	66.88	119.18	192.58	119.18	0.26	0.35	1.70
63	30	66.84	119.18	193.03	119.18	0.26	0.34	1.70
63.5	15	66.79	119.18	193.48	119.18	0.26	0.34	1.70
64	32	66.71	119.16	193.92	119.16	0.26	0.33	1.70
64.5	18	66.61	119.09	194.31	119.09	0.26	0.32	1.70
65	26	66.48	118.97	194.65	118.97	0.27	0.31	1.70
65.5	18	66.30	118.79	194.9	118.79	0.27	0.30	1.70
66	13	66.07	118.54	195.07	118.54	0.27	0.30	1.70
66.5	23	65.79	118.20	195.14	118.20	0.27	0.29	1.70
67	18	65.45	117.78	195.09	117.78	0.27	0.28	1.70
67.5	17	65.04	117.27	194.92	117.27	0.27	0.27	1.70

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th Perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
68	21	64.58	116.66	194.62	116.66	0.27	0.26	1.70
68.5	16	64.06	115.97	194.22	115.97	0.28	0.25	1.70
69	15	63.49	115.21	193.73	115.21	0.28	0.25	1.70
69.5	23	62.88	114.38	193.15	114.38	0.28	0.24	1.70
70	26	62.23	113.50	192.51	113.50	0.28	0.23	1.70
70.5	24	61.55	112.58	191.83	112.58	0.28	0.22	1.70
71	18	60.85	111.63	191.12	111.63	0.28	0.21	1.71
71.5	13	60.13	110.67	190.41	110.67	0.29	0.20	1.71
72	27	59.41	109.7	189.72	109.70	0.29	0.19	1.71
72.5	24	58.69	108.74	189.05	108.74	0.29	0.19	1.71
73	25	57.97	107.79	188.43	107.79	0.29	0.18	1.71
73.5	23	57.27	106.86	187.87	106.86	0.30	0.17	1.71
74	22	56.58	105.97	187.37	105.97	0.30	0.16	1.71
74.5	10	55.90	105.11	186.96	105.11	0.30	0.15	1.72
75	17	55.26	104.3	186.64	104.30	0.30	0.14	1.72
75.5	7	54.63	103.52	186.4	103.52	0.31	0.14	1.72
76	9	54.03	102.79	186.25	102.79	0.31	0.13	1.72
76.5	9	53.45	102.10	186.18	102.10	0.31	0.12	1.72
77	13	52.89	101.44	186.19	101.44	0.31	0.11	1.73
77.5	9	52.35	100.82	186.28	100.82	0.32	0.10	1.73
78	2	51.82	100.22	186.42	100.22	0.32	0.09	1.73
78.5	9	51.31	99.65	186.63	99.65	0.32	0.09	1.73
79	3	50.82	99.10	186.9	99.10	0.33	0.08	1.74
79.5	9	50.34	98.57	187.21	98.57	0.33	0.07	1.74
80	1	49.87	98.05	187.56	98.05	0.33	0.06	1.74

2B: Females who were not taking CDs or HRT

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	Nu	tau
0.25	53	13.01	43.35	89.26	43.34	0.45	0.54	2.00
0.5	103	13.68	44.75	91.79	44.75	0.45	0.54	1.98
0.75	19	14.60	46.65	95.19	46.65	0.44	0.53	1.97
1	66	15.74	48.99	99.35	48.99	0.44	0.52	1.95
1.5	21	18.68	54.84	109.56	54.84	0.42	0.51	1.91
2	41	22.40	61.84	121.41	61.84	0.40	0.49	1.87
2.5	45	26.69	69.37	133.57	69.37	0.39	0.47	1.83
3	41	31.38	76.95	145.14	76.95	0.37	0.46	1.79
3.5	37	36.28	84.22	155.51	84.22	0.35	0.44	1.76
4	42	41.29	91.03	164.56	91.03	0.34	0.42	1.74
4.5	50	46.46	97.53	172.72	97.53	0.32	0.40	1.72
5	55	51.78	103.78	180.31	103.78	0.31	0.37	1.71
5.5	46	57.25	109.93	187.83	109.93	0.29	0.33	1.70
6	57	63.19	116.73	196.67	116.73	0.28	0.29	1.70
6.5	51	69.66	124.34	207.30	124.34	0.27	0.23	1.72
7	71	75.31	130.71	216.68	130.71	0.26	0.16	1.76
7.5	42	79.99	136.02	225.63	136.02	0.26	0.09	1.84
8	67	84.68	142.27	238.08	142.27	0.26	0.02	1.95
8.5	53	89.71	150.18	255.83	150.18	0.27	-0.06	2.11
9	65	95.63	160.96	282.12	160.96	0.28	-0.14	2.29
9.5	50	102.11	174.29	317.18	174.29	0.30	-0.20	2.49
10	74	107.77	187.84	355.23	187.84	0.31	-0.23	2.66
10.5	53	113.65	203.78	397.08	203.78	0.33	-0.21	2.76
11	74	121.79	225.30	442.34	225.30	0.34	-0.14	2.77
11.5	50	136.18	257.01	490.05	257.01	0.34	-0.03	2.71
12	78	160.11	299.24	534.34	299.24	0.32	0.13	2.58
12.5	60	189.12	339.23	559.12	339.23	0.28	0.29	2.41
13	74	210.40	361.41	557.81	361.41	0.25	0.45	2.24
13.5	60	215.35	365.29	544.04	365.29	0.23	0.61	2.10
14	70	200.12	348.61	500.61	348.61	0.22	0.95	1.86
14.5	69	190.62	333.47	480.38	333.47	0.22	0.94	1.88
15	52	181.45	319.59	462.24	319.59	0.22	0.93	1.90
15.5	50	172.35	306.51	445.52	306.51	0.23	0.92	1.91
16	35	163.13	293.85	429.65	293.85	0.23	0.92	1.92
16.5	37	153.95	281.69	414.70	281.69	0.24	0.92	1.92
17	24	145.56	270.95	401.79	270.95	0.24	0.91	1.93
17.5	16	138.52	262.35	391.88	262.35	0.25	0.91	1.92
18	11	133.04	256.04	385.09	256.04	0.25	0.91	1.92
18.5	7	128.71	251.08	379.99	251.08	0.25	0.90	1.91
19	2	125.16	246.57	375.14	246.57	0.26	0.89	1.91
19.5	2	122.10	241.87	369.54	241.87	0.26	0.88	1.90
20	4	119.50	236.93	363.13	236.93	0.26	0.87	1.90
20.5	13	117.38	231.96	356.31	231.96	0.26	0.85	1.90
21	42	115.73	227.13	349.39	227.13	0.26	0.83	1.90
21.5	27	114.53	222.57	342.65	222.57	0.26	0.80	1.90
22	23	113.65	218.36	336.38	218.36	0.26	0.77	1.91

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	Nu	tau
22.5	21	112.98	214.59	330.81	214.59	0.26	0.74	1.91
23	13	112.46	211.31	326.14	211.31	0.26	0.71	1.92
23.5	15	112.01	208.49	322.38	208.49	0.26	0.68	1.94
24	8	111.59	205.94	319.15	205.94	0.26	0.64	1.95
24.5	6	111.14	203.44	316.05	203.44	0.26	0.61	1.96
25	7	110.58	200.84	312.75	200.84	0.26	0.58	1.97
25.5	6	109.90	197.99	308.98	197.99	0.26	0.54	1.98
26	12	109.12	194.96	304.76	194.96	0.26	0.51	2.00
26.5	5	108.33	191.87	300.26	191.87	0.26	0.48	2.01
27	6	107.59	188.81	295.60	188.81	0.25	0.45	2.02
27.5	5	106.96	185.88	290.90	185.88	0.25	0.42	2.02
28	14	106.47	183.14	286.26	183.14	0.25	0.39	2.03
28.5	10	106.12	180.61	281.77	180.61	0.25	0.37	2.04
29	9	105.88	178.30	277.48	178.30	0.24	0.34	2.04
29.5	9	105.75	176.22	273.47	176.22	0.24	0.32	2.05
30	9	105.70	174.38	269.78	174.38	0.24	0.29	2.05
30.5	5	105.73	172.76	266.45	172.76	0.24	0.27	2.05
31	5	105.83	171.36	263.48	171.36	0.23	0.25	2.05
31.5	5	105.98	170.16	260.84	170.16	0.23	0.23	2.04
32	3	106.17	169.12	258.51	169.12	0.23	0.21	2.04
32.5	1	106.38	168.24	256.47	168.24	0.22	0.19	2.04
33	5	106.61	167.49	254.70	167.49	0.22	0.17	2.03
33.5	5	106.84	166.85	253.18	166.85	0.22	0.15	2.02
34	8	107.05	166.28	251.85	166.28	0.22	0.14	2.02
34.5	0	107.23	165.76	250.66	165.76	0.22	0.12	2.01
35	7	107.34	165.23	249.55	165.23	0.22	0.11	2.00
35.5	2	107.37	164.68	248.49	164.68	0.21	0.09	1.98
36	6	107.30	164.07	247.44	164.07	0.21	0.08	1.97
36.5	2	107.11	163.38	246.35	163.38	0.21	0.07	1.96
37	4	106.79	162.59	245.21	162.59	0.21	0.06	1.95
37.5	1	106.35	161.71	244.02	161.71	0.21	0.04	1.93
38	9	105.78	160.72	242.78	160.72	0.21	0.03	1.92
38.5	3	105.08	159.64	241.50	159.64	0.21	0.02	1.91
39	6	104.25	158.45	240.16	158.45	0.21	0.02	1.89
39.5	5	103.29	157.17	238.79	157.17	0.21	0.01	1.88
40	1	102.20	155.78	237.37	155.78	0.21	0.00	1.86
40.5	10	101.00	154.31	235.93	154.31	0.21	0.00	1.85
41	29	99.71	152.77	234.48	152.77	0.22	-0.01	1.83
41.5	27	98.34	151.17	233.02	151.17	0.22	-0.01	1.82
42	33	96.90	149.54	231.59	149.54	0.22	-0.02	1.81
42.5	29	95.42	147.89	230.19	147.89	0.22	-0.02	1.79
43	38	93.91	146.22	228.82	146.22	0.22	-0.03	1.78
43.5	36	92.37	144.56	227.51	144.56	0.23	-0.03	1.77
44	33	90.82	142.91	226.26	142.91	0.23	-0.03	1.75
44.5	29	89.27	141.27	225.06	141.27	0.23	-0.03	1.74
45	35	87.73	139.66	223.91	139.66	0.23	-0.03	1.73
45.5	25	86.20	138.09	222.80	138.09	0.24	-0.03	1.72
46	27	84.71	136.56	221.74	136.56	0.24	-0.03	1.71

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	Nu	tau
46.5	22	83.26	135.07	220.70	135.07	0.24	-0.03	1.70
47	25	81.85	133.63	219.69	133.63	0.25	-0.03	1.69
47.5	31	80.49	132.25	218.70	132.25	0.25	-0.03	1.68
48	23	79.18	130.93	217.72	130.93	0.25	-0.02	1.68
48.5	23	77.94	129.67	216.75	129.67	0.26	-0.02	1.67
49	33	76.76	128.48	215.78	128.48	0.26	-0.01	1.67
49.5	23	75.65	127.36	214.81	127.36	0.26	-0.01	1.66
50	36	74.62	126.32	213.85	126.32	0.26	0.00	1.66
50.5	22	73.66	125.36	212.87	125.36	0.26	0.01	1.66
51	30	72.79	124.49	211.90	124.49	0.27	0.02	1.66
51.5	16	72.00	123.70	210.91	123.70	0.27	0.03	1.66
52	30	71.30	123.00	209.92	123.00	0.27	0.04	1.66
52.5	28	70.69	122.38	208.92	122.38	0.27	0.05	1.67
53	25	70.16	121.85	207.90	121.85	0.27	0.06	1.67
53.5	25	69.70	121.37	206.85	121.37	0.27	0.07	1.67
54	22	69.28	120.93	205.76	120.93	0.27	0.09	1.68
54.5	18	68.91	120.52	204.62	120.52	0.27	0.10	1.69
55	22	68.57	120.12	203.42	120.12	0.27	0.11	1.69
55.5	21	68.24	119.71	202.16	119.71	0.27	0.13	1.70
56	29	67.93	119.28	200.81	119.28	0.27	0.14	1.71
56.5	20	67.61	118.83	199.39	118.83	0.27	0.16	1.72
57	15	67.28	118.34	197.88	118.34	0.27	0.17	1.73
57.5	18	66.93	117.79	196.28	117.79	0.27	0.19	1.74
58	18	66.56	117.20	194.59	117.20	0.27	0.20	1.75
58.5	21	66.18	116.56	192.85	116.56	0.27	0.22	1.76
59	18	65.78	115.89	191.06	115.89	0.27	0.23	1.77
59.5	18	65.37	115.19	189.25	115.19	0.27	0.25	1.78
60	14	64.95	114.46	187.42	114.46	0.26	0.26	1.79
60.5	23	64.52	113.72	185.59	113.72	0.26	0.28	1.80
61	27	64.09	112.96	183.78	112.96	0.26	0.29	1.81
61.5	25	63.64	112.19	182.00	112.19	0.26	0.30	1.82
62	25	63.20	111.41	180.24	111.41	0.26	0.31	1.84
62.5	30	62.75	110.64	178.53	110.64	0.26	0.33	1.85
63	27	62.31	109.86	176.87	109.86	0.26	0.34	1.86
63.5	29	61.86	109.10	175.27	109.10	0.26	0.35	1.87
64	21	61.41	108.33	173.72	108.33	0.26	0.36	1.89
64.5	17	60.96	107.58	172.23	107.58	0.26	0.36	1.90
65	13	60.52	106.84	170.80	106.84	0.26	0.37	1.91
65.5	11	60.08	106.12	169.44	106.12	0.26	0.38	1.93
66	19	59.64	105.41	168.14	105.41	0.26	0.38	1.94
66.5	20	59.20	104.71	166.90	104.71	0.26	0.39	1.96
67	18	58.77	104.03	165.74	104.03	0.26	0.40	1.97
67.5	12	58.34	103.38	164.64	103.38	0.26	0.40	1.98
68	15	57.92	102.74	163.62	102.74	0.26	0.40	2.00
68.5	31	57.50	102.12	162.67	102.12	0.26	0.41	2.01
69	23	57.08	101.53	161.78	101.53	0.26	0.41	2.03
69.5	15	56.67	100.95	160.97	100.95	0.26	0.41	2.04
70	17	56.27	100.40	160.22	100.40	0.26	0.41	2.06

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	Nu	tau
70.5	15	55.87	99.86	159.53	99.86	0.26	0.41	2.07
71	16	55.47	99.34	158.89	99.34	0.27	0.41	2.09
71.5	22	55.07	98.83	158.29	98.83	0.27	0.41	2.10
72	21	54.67	98.33	157.75	98.33	0.27	0.41	2.12
72.5	16	54.28	97.84	157.24	97.84	0.27	0.41	2.13
73	18	53.89	97.37	156.76	97.37	0.27	0.41	2.15
73.5	17	53.49	96.90	156.32	96.90	0.27	0.41	2.16
74	14	53.10	96.44	155.91	96.44	0.27	0.40	2.18
74.5	11	52.71	95.99	155.52	95.99	0.28	0.40	2.19
75	16	52.32	95.54	155.15	95.54	0.28	0.40	2.21
75.5	7	51.93	95.10	154.81	95.10	0.28	0.40	2.23
76	6	51.53	94.66	154.48	94.66	0.28	0.40	2.24
76.5	11	51.14	94.22	154.17	94.22	0.28	0.39	2.26
77	7	50.75	93.79	153.88	93.79	0.28	0.39	2.27
77.5	7	50.36	93.37	153.61	93.37	0.29	0.39	2.29
78	8	49.98	92.95	153.35	92.95	0.29	0.38	2.30
78.5	10	49.59	92.54	153.11	92.54	0.29	0.38	2.32
79	9	49.21	92.13	152.88	92.13	0.29	0.38	2.33
79.5	3	48.83	91.73	152.67	91.73	0.29	0.38	2.35
80	3	48.46	91.34	152.47	91.34	0.29	0.37	2.37

2C: Females who were taking or not taking CDs or HRT

Age [years]	n	2.5th Perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
0.25	53	12.42	43.20	86.36	43.20	0.44	0.63	2.02
0.5	103	13.10	44.72	89.19	44.72	0.44	0.62	2.02
0.75	19	14.02	46.75	92.94	46.75	0.44	0.61	2.00
1	66	15.17	49.22	97.50	49.22	0.43	0.60	1.99
1.5	21	18.12	55.34	108.65	55.34	0.42	0.57	1.96
2	41	21.87	62.58	121.49	62.58	0.41	0.55	1.93
2.5	45	26.22	70.21	134.44	70.21	0.39	0.52	1.90
3	41	31.00	77.72	146.44	77.72	0.38	0.49	1.88
3.5	37	36.15	84.87	156.92	84.87	0.36	0.45	1.85
4	42	41.57	91.57	165.82	91.57	0.34	0.41	1.82
4.5	50	47.23	97.91	173.56	97.91	0.32	0.37	1.80
5	55	53.02	104.01	180.72	104.01	0.30	0.32	1.79
5.5	46	58.67	109.83	187.78	109.83	0.29	0.27	1.78
6	57	64.14	115.63	195.60	115.63	0.28	0.21	1.78
6.5	51	69.60	121.90	205.22	121.90	0.27	0.14	1.80
7	71	74.91	128.47	216.58	128.47	0.27	0.06	1.85
7.5	42	79.85	135.03	229.27	135.03	0.27	-0.01	1.93
8	67	84.57	141.75	243.44	141.75	0.27	-0.09	2.04
8.5	53	89.94	150.29	262.39	150.29	0.28	-0.15	2.17
9	65	96.64	162.27	290.29	162.27	0.28	-0.21	2.32
9.5	50	103.11	175.70	325.22	175.70	0.30	-0.25	2.47
10	74	108.16	188.77	362.93	188.77	0.32	-0.27	2.59
10.5	53	112.77	202.62	400.42	202.62	0.33	-0.24	2.65
11	74	120.68	222.42	439.01	222.42	0.34	-0.16	2.64
11.5	50	137.78	256.14	485.45	256.14	0.33	-0.05	2.58
12	78	164.78	302.13	535.82	302.13	0.31	0.10	2.46
12.5	60	193.38	343.78	568.80	343.78	0.28	0.25	2.32
13	74	211.55	365.41	573.45	365.41	0.25	0.39	2.19
13.5	60	212.69	363.06	553.03	363.06	0.24	0.50	2.07
14	70	197.97	348.36	501.74	348.36	0.22	0.96	1.84
14.5	72	186.11	330.90	480.75	330.90	0.23	0.93	1.83
15	56	175.57	315.73	462.89	315.73	0.23	0.90	1.82
15.5	57	165.99	302.21	447.24	302.21	0.24	0.87	1.82
16	44	157.05	289.75	432.93	289.75	0.24	0.84	1.80
16.5	48	148.70	278.14	419.66	278.14	0.25	0.82	1.79
17	33	141.28	267.80	407.96	267.80	0.25	0.80	1.78
17.5	23	135.05	259.08	398.29	259.08	0.26	0.78	1.76
18	22	130.05	251.96	390.62	251.96	0.26	0.76	1.75
18.5	17	125.92	245.70	383.81	245.70	0.26	0.74	1.73
19	5	122.34	239.61	376.78	239.61	0.27	0.71	1.72
19.5	4	119.07	233.24	368.80	233.24	0.27	0.69	1.71
20	9	116.13	226.81	360.27	226.81	0.27	0.66	1.70
20.5	24	113.66	220.72	351.99	220.72	0.27	0.63	1.70
21	70	111.72	215.31	344.58	215.31	0.27	0.60	1.70
21.5	48	110.34	210.75	338.41	210.75	0.27	0.56	1.70
22	50	109.39	206.95	333.46	206.95	0.27	0.52	1.71

Age [years]	n	2.5th Perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
22.5	35	108.77	203.84	329.64	203.84	0.27	0.49	1.73
23	23	108.37	201.33	326.90	201.33	0.27	0.45	1.74
23.5	25	108.12	199.30	325.05	199.30	0.27	0.41	1.76
24	16	107.89	197.45	323.55	197.45	0.27	0.37	1.78
24.5	11	107.58	195.52	321.86	195.52	0.27	0.33	1.81
25	13	107.08	193.28	319.50	193.28	0.27	0.30	1.83
25.5	9	106.32	190.57	316.11	190.57	0.27	0.26	1.86
26	21	105.38	187.50	311.82	187.50	0.27	0.23	1.88
26.5	11	104.37	184.28	306.95	184.28	0.27	0.20	1.91
27	10	103.40	181.10	301.81	181.10	0.27	0.17	1.94
27.5	7	102.57	178.11	296.63	178.11	0.27	0.15	1.96
28	21	101.94	175.43	291.62	175.43	0.27	0.13	1.98
28.5	16	101.52	173.07	286.88	173.07	0.26	0.10	2.01
29	12	101.28	171.05	282.50	171.05	0.26	0.09	2.03
29.5	13	101.20	169.36	278.52	169.36	0.26	0.07	2.05
30	15	101.29	167.99	275.01	167.99	0.26	0.05	2.06
30.5	8	101.53	166.95	271.99	166.95	0.25	0.04	2.08
31	10	101.89	166.18	269.43	166.18	0.25	0.03	2.09
31.5	5	102.33	165.63	267.22	165.63	0.25	0.01	2.10
32	7	102.80	165.21	265.28	165.21	0.24	0.00	2.11
32.5	2	103.27	164.87	263.53	164.87	0.24	-0.01	2.11
33	9	103.70	164.58	261.92	164.58	0.24	-0.01	2.11
33.5	6	104.08	164.27	260.37	164.27	0.24	-0.02	2.11
34	11	104.36	163.91	258.84	163.91	0.23	-0.03	2.11
34.5	1	104.54	163.48	257.30	163.48	0.23	-0.03	2.11
35	8	104.60	162.95	255.71	162.95	0.23	-0.04	2.10
35.5	2	104.52	162.31	254.04	162.31	0.23	-0.04	2.10
36	9	104.29	161.52	252.27	161.52	0.23	-0.04	2.09
36.5	2	103.90	160.57	250.38	160.57	0.23	-0.05	2.08
37	7	103.35	159.48	248.37	159.48	0.22	-0.05	2.07
37.5	3	102.67	158.26	246.30	158.26	0.22	-0.05	2.05
38	11	101.85	156.94	244.19	156.94	0.22	-0.05	2.04
38.5	4	100.93	155.55	242.09	155.55	0.22	-0.05	2.02
39	7	99.92	154.10	240.02	154.10	0.22	-0.05	2.01
39.5	6	98.82	152.61	238.02	152.61	0.22	-0.05	1.99
40	3	97.65	151.09	236.09	151.09	0.22	-0.05	1.97
40.5	15	96.42	149.57	234.27	149.57	0.23	-0.05	1.96
41	41	95.15	148.04	232.55	148.04	0.23	-0.05	1.94
41.5	31	93.83	146.52	230.93	146.52	0.23	-0.05	1.92
42	44	92.48	145.00	229.42	145.00	0.23	-0.04	1.90
42.5	38	91.11	143.51	228.02	143.51	0.23	-0.04	1.88
43	56	89.72	142.03	226.73	142.03	0.23	-0.04	1.86
43.5	44	88.32	140.58	225.54	140.58	0.24	-0.04	1.85
44	47	86.91	139.16	224.47	139.16	0.24	-0.03	1.83
44.5	34	85.51	137.78	223.50	137.78	0.24	-0.03	1.81
45	50	84.12	136.43	222.61	136.43	0.24	-0.03	1.79
45.5	36	82.75	135.12	221.80	135.12	0.25	-0.02	1.78
46	37	81.40	133.86	221.05	133.86	0.25	-0.02	1.76

Age [years]	n	2.5th Perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
46.5	28	80.10	132.64	220.34	132.64	0.25	-0.01	1.75
47	32	78.83	131.47	219.67	131.47	0.26	-0.01	1.74
47.5	40	77.62	130.35	219.03	130.35	0.26	0.00	1.72
48	37	76.45	129.29	218.40	129.29	0.26	0.00	1.71
48.5	39	75.34	128.27	217.77	128.27	0.27	0.01	1.70
49	41	74.29	127.31	217.13	127.31	0.27	0.02	1.69
49.5	35	73.30	126.4	216.47	126.40	0.27	0.02	1.69
50	52	72.37	125.55	215.78	125.55	0.27	0.03	1.68
50.5	30	71.52	124.75	215.05	124.75	0.27	0.04	1.67
51	36	70.73	124.00	214.27	124.00	0.28	0.05	1.67
51.5	18	70.02	123.31	213.43	123.31	0.28	0.06	1.66
52	34	69.38	122.66	212.54	122.66	0.28	0.06	1.66
52.5	33	68.81	122.07	211.57	122.07	0.28	0.07	1.66
53	31	68.32	121.53	210.54	121.53	0.28	0.08	1.66
53.5	32	67.88	121.01	209.43	121.01	0.28	0.09	1.66
54	23	67.49	120.52	208.27	120.52	0.28	0.10	1.66
54.5	20	67.14	120.05	207.04	120.05	0.28	0.11	1.66
55	25	66.82	119.58	205.75	119.58	0.28	0.12	1.66
55.5	23	66.52	119.11	204.41	119.11	0.28	0.14	1.67
56	32	66.23	118.63	203.00	118.63	0.28	0.15	1.67
56.5	21	65.95	118.13	201.54	118.13	0.28	0.16	1.68
57	16	65.67	117.61	200.03	117.61	0.28	0.17	1.68
57.5	20	65.38	117.06	198.47	117.06	0.28	0.18	1.69
58	22	65.09	116.49	196.86	116.49	0.28	0.19	1.69
58.5	24	64.78	115.89	195.22	115.89	0.27	0.20	1.70
59	19	64.47	115.27	193.56	115.27	0.27	0.21	1.71
59.5	18	64.15	114.63	191.90	114.63	0.27	0.22	1.71
60	15	63.82	113.97	190.23	113.97	0.27	0.23	1.72
60.5	24	63.49	113.3	188.56	113.30	0.27	0.24	1.73
61	30	63.15	112.62	186.91	112.62	0.27	0.24	1.74
61.5	27	62.80	111.93	185.28	111.93	0.27	0.25	1.75
62	25	62.44	111.23	183.67	111.23	0.27	0.26	1.76
62.5	30	62.08	110.53	182.10	110.53	0.27	0.27	1.77
63	31	61.72	109.83	180.56	109.83	0.27	0.28	1.78
63.5	30	61.34	109.12	179.06	109.12	0.27	0.28	1.79
64	23	60.96	108.42	177.6	108.42	0.27	0.29	1.80
64.5	18	60.58	107.72	176.18	107.72	0.27	0.29	1.81
65	15	60.20	107.02	174.8	107.02	0.27	0.30	1.82
65.5	12	59.81	106.33	173.47	106.33	0.27	0.30	1.83
66	19	59.42	105.65	172.17	105.65	0.27	0.31	1.85
66.5	22	59.03	104.97	170.93	104.97	0.27	0.31	1.86
67	19	58.64	104.31	169.72	104.31	0.27	0.32	1.87
67.5	12	58.25	103.65	168.57	103.65	0.27	0.32	1.88
68	16	57.86	103.00	167.46	103.00	0.27	0.32	1.89
68.5	32	57.47	102.37	166.39	102.37	0.27	0.33	1.91
69	27	57.09	101.74	165.38	101.74	0.27	0.33	1.92
69.5	18	56.70	101.13	164.41	101.13	0.27	0.33	1.93
70	18	56.32	100.53	163.48	100.53	0.27	0.33	1.95

Age [years]	n	2.5th Perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
70.5	17	55.94	99.95	162.59	99.95	0.27	0.33	1.96
71	18	55.56	99.37	161.75	99.37	0.27	0.33	1.98
71.5	25	55.18	98.81	160.94	98.81	0.27	0.33	1.99
72	22	54.81	98.25	160.17	98.25	0.27	0.33	2.00
72.5	16	54.43	97.71	159.43	97.71	0.27	0.33	2.02
73	20	54.06	97.18	158.72	97.18	0.27	0.33	2.03
73.5	18	53.69	96.66	158.05	96.66	0.27	0.33	2.05
74	14	53.32	96.14	157.40	96.14	0.27	0.33	2.06
74.5	11	52.96	95.64	156.78	95.64	0.28	0.33	2.07
75	17	52.59	95.15	156.19	95.15	0.28	0.33	2.09
75.5	7	52.23	94.66	155.63	94.66	0.28	0.33	2.10
76	6	51.87	94.19	155.09	94.19	0.28	0.33	2.12
76.5	12	51.52	93.73	154.57	93.73	0.28	0.33	2.13
77	7	51.16	93.27	154.08	93.27	0.28	0.33	2.15
77.5	7	50.81	92.82	153.60	92.82	0.28	0.32	2.16
78	8	50.46	92.38	153.15	92.38	0.28	0.32	2.18
78.5	10	50.12	91.95	152.71	91.95	0.28	0.32	2.19
79	9	49.78	91.53	152.29	91.53	0.29	0.32	2.20
79.5	3	49.44	91.12	151.89	91.12	0.29	0.32	2.22
80	5	49.11	90.71	151.5	90.71	0.29	0.32	2.23

Suppl. Table 3: Age-dependent percentiles of IGFBP-3 (ng/mL) for children, adolescents, and adults (n = number of samples). (A) Males, (B) Females who were not taking CDs or HRT, (C) Females who were taking or not taking CDs or HRT

3A: Males

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
0.25	71	936.85	1646.37	2595.57	1646.37	0.26	0.42	2.04
0.5	109	966.75	1691.53	2658.25	1691.53	0.25	0.42	2.03
0.75	36	997.39	1737.76	2722.38	1737.76	0.25	0.42	2.03
1	74	1028.79	1785.06	2787.95	1785.06	0.25	0.43	2.03
1.5	27	1093.83	1882.80	2923.26	1882.80	0.25	0.43	2.03
2	43	1161.79	1984.6	3063.94	1984.60	0.24	0.43	2.03
2.5	56	1232.57	2090.27	3209.66	2090.28	0.24	0.44	2.03
3	50	1306.01	2199.55	3359.99	2199.55	0.24	0.44	2.03
3.5	55	1381.92	2312.09	3514.44	2312.09	0.24	0.44	2.02
4	53	1460.05	2427.49	3672.38	2427.49	0.23	0.45	2.02
4.5	49	1540.09	2545.26	3833.10	2545.26	0.23	0.45	2.02
5	56	1621.69	2664.85	3995.78	2664.85	0.23	0.45	2.02
5.5	51	1704.50	2785.72	4159.68	2785.72	0.22	0.46	2.02
6	65	1788.24	2907.44	4324.18	2907.44	0.22	0.46	2.02
6.5	63	1872.58	3029.54	4488.65	3029.54	0.22	0.46	2.01
7	65	1957.18	3151.51	4652.37	3151.51	0.22	0.47	2.01
7.5	58	2041.65	3272.79	4814.60	3272.79	0.22	0.47	2.01
8	77	2125.60	3392.83	4974.56	3392.82	0.21	0.47	2.01
8.5	84	2208.61	3511.00	5131.43	3511.00	0.21	0.48	2.01
9	79	2290.24	3626.67	5284.36	3626.67	0.21	0.48	2.01
9.5	82	2370.02	3739.21	5432.48	3739.21	0.21	0.48	2.00
10	76	2447.50	3847.92	5574.88	3847.92	0.21	0.49	2.00
10.5	88	2522.18	3952.14	5710.65	3952.14	0.21	0.49	2.00
11	70	2593.58	4051.17	5838.90	4051.17	0.20	0.49	2.00
11.5	75	2661.21	4144.33	5958.71	4144.33	0.20	0.49	2.00
12	77	2724.59	4230.94	6069.18	4230.94	0.20	0.50	2.00
12.5	74	2783.23	4310.35	6169.46	4310.35	0.20	0.50	1.99
13	64	2836.69	4381.9	6258.71	4381.90	0.20	0.50	1.99
13.5	66	2884.52	4445.00	6336.12	4445.00	0.20	0.51	1.99
14	67	2926.30	4499.07	6400.97	4499.07	0.20	0.51	1.99
14.5	73	2961.65	4543.58	6452.58	4543.58	0.20	0.51	1.99
15	61	2990.22	4578.06	6490.34	4578.06	0.19	0.52	1.99
15.5	49	3011.70	4602.09	6513.73	4602.09	0.19	0.52	1.98
16	56	3025.94	4615.51	6522.56	4615.51	0.19	0.52	1.98
16.5	23	3033.45	4619.13	6518.05	4619.13	0.19	0.52	1.98
17	27	3035.01	4614.17	6501.95	4614.17	0.19	0.53	1.98
17.5	15	3031.44	4601.89	6476.08	4601.89	0.19	0.53	1.98
18	12	3023.57	4583.58	6442.26	4583.58	0.19	0.53	1.98
18.5	13	3012.25	4560.55	6402.32	4560.55	0.19	0.54	1.97
19	5	2998.34	4534.06	6358.07	4534.06	0.19	0.54	1.97
19.5	2	2982.68	4505.4	6311.27	4505.40	0.19	0.54	1.97

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
20	4	2966.11	4475.81	6263.65	4475.81	0.19	0.54	1.97
20.5	19	2949.43	4446.49	6216.89	4446.49	0.19	0.55	1.97
21	35	2933.45	4418.63	6172.61	4418.63	0.19	0.55	1.97
21.5	24	2918.76	4393.11	6132.02	4393.11	0.19	0.55	1.96
22	30	2905.41	4369.98	6095.16	4369.98	0.19	0.55	1.96
22.5	9	2893.35	4349.14	6061.87	4349.14	0.19	0.56	1.96
23	17	2882.54	4330.51	6032.02	4330.51	0.19	0.56	1.96
23.5	8	2872.92	4313.99	6005.45	4313.99	0.18	0.56	1.96
24	20	2864.45	4299.51	5982.03	4299.51	0.18	0.56	1.96
24.5	8	2857.08	4286.98	5961.64	4286.98	0.18	0.57	1.95
25	18	2850.79	4276.34	5944.16	4276.34	0.18	0.57	1.95
25.5	13	2845.51	4267.50	5929.46	4267.50	0.18	0.57	1.95
26	17	2841.22	4260.39	5917.44	4260.39	0.18	0.57	1.95
26.5	11	2837.88	4254.95	5907.98	4254.95	0.18	0.58	1.95
27	12	2835.40	4251.06	5900.92	4251.06	0.18	0.58	1.95
27.5	9	2833.65	4248.51	5895.95	4248.51	0.18	0.58	1.94
28	23	2832.51	4247.08	5892.78	4247.08	0.18	0.58	1.94
28.5	11	2831.83	4246.57	5891.10	4246.57	0.18	0.58	1.94
29	17	2831.47	4246.77	5890.60	4246.77	0.18	0.59	1.94
29.5	18	2831.31	4247.46	5891.01	4247.46	0.18	0.59	1.94
30	14	2831.19	4248.43	5892.00	4248.43	0.18	0.59	1.94
30.5	14	2830.99	4249.48	5893.29	4249.48	0.18	0.59	1.93
31	13	2830.57	4250.39	5894.58	4250.39	0.18	0.60	1.93
31.5	10	2829.78	4250.95	5895.57	4250.95	0.18	0.60	1.93
32	8	2828.50	4250.95	5895.96	4250.95	0.18	0.60	1.93
32.5	7	2826.66	4250.29	5895.61	4250.29	0.18	0.60	1.93
33	10	2824.28	4248.98	5894.53	4248.98	0.18	0.60	1.93
33.5	4	2821.35	4247.04	5892.74	4247.04	0.18	0.61	1.92
34	12	2817.91	4244.48	5890.25	4244.48	0.18	0.61	1.92
34.5	5	2813.95	4241.30	5887.07	4241.30	0.18	0.61	1.92
35	7	2809.49	4237.54	5883.22	4237.54	0.18	0.61	1.92
35.5	5	2804.55	4233.19	5878.72	4233.19	0.18	0.61	1.92
36	11	2799.13	4228.27	5873.56	4228.27	0.18	0.62	1.92
36.5	6	2793.25	4222.81	5867.79	4222.81	0.19	0.62	1.92
37	7	2786.92	4216.80	5861.39	4216.80	0.19	0.62	1.91
37.5	6	2780.16	4210.26	5854.40	4210.26	0.19	0.62	1.91
38	17	2772.98	4203.24	5846.86	4203.24	0.19	0.62	1.91
38.5	3	2765.43	4195.76	5838.82	4195.76	0.19	0.62	1.91
39	13	2757.52	4187.89	5830.35	4187.89	0.19	0.63	1.91
39.5	5	2749.30	4179.66	5821.50	4179.66	0.19	0.63	1.91
40	3	2740.80	4171.11	5812.33	4171.11	0.19	0.63	1.90
40.5	4	2732.04	4162.29	5802.89	4162.29	0.19	0.63	1.90
41	34	2723.06	4153.24	5793.25	4153.24	0.19	0.63	1.90
41.5	38	2713.88	4144.00	5783.46	4144.00	0.19	0.63	1.90
42	46	2704.54	4134.61	5773.57	4134.61	0.19	0.64	1.90
42.5	35	2695.05	4125.12	5763.64	4125.12	0.19	0.64	1.90
43	45	2685.47	4115.58	5753.75	4115.58	0.19	0.64	1.90
43.5	37	2675.84	4106.08	5744.03	4106.08	0.19	0.64	1.89

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
44	56	2666.26	4096.76	5734.65	4096.76	0.19	0.64	1.89
44.5	47	2656.81	4087.73	5725.79	4087.73	0.19	0.64	1.89
45	52	2647.56	4079.11	5717.62	4079.11	0.19	0.64	1.89
45.5	37	2638.58	4071.03	5710.29	4071.03	0.19	0.65	1.89
46	31	2629.95	4063.59	5703.98	4063.59	0.19	0.65	1.89
46.5	46	2621.75	4056.91	5698.86	4056.91	0.19	0.65	1.88
47	46	2614.04	4051.12	5695.08	4051.12	0.19	0.65	1.88
47.5	36	2606.91	4046.32	5692.81	4046.32	0.19	0.65	1.88
48	43	2600.41	4042.64	5692.23	4042.64	0.19	0.65	1.88
48.5	32	2594.55	4040.07	5693.34	4040.07	0.19	0.65	1.88
49	36	2589.12	4038.31	5695.72	4038.31	0.20	0.65	1.88
49.5	45	2583.90	4037.01	5698.87	4037.01	0.20	0.66	1.88
50	37	2578.66	4035.8	5702.29	4035.8	0.20	0.66	1.87
50.5	43	2573.15	4034.33	5705.47	4034.33	0.20	0.66	1.87
51	41	2567.16	4032.24	5707.91	4032.24	0.20	0.66	1.87
51.5	24	2560.46	4029.17	5709.10	4029.17	0.20	0.66	1.87
52	21	2552.82	4024.77	5708.54	4024.77	0.20	0.66	1.87
52.5	37	2544.02	4018.68	5705.72	4018.68	0.20	0.66	1.87
53	21	2533.85	4010.55	5700.13	4010.55	0.20	0.66	1.86
53.5	31	2522.09	4000.04	5691.30	4000.04	0.20	0.66	1.86
54	29	2508.73	3987.12	5679.15	3987.12	0.20	0.66	1.86
54.5	20	2494.05	3972.22	5664.32	3972.22	0.20	0.67	1.86
55	20	2478.37	3955.83	5647.47	3955.83	0.20	0.67	1.86
55.5	22	2461.98	3938.41	5629.28	3938.41	0.20	0.67	1.86
56	26	2445.17	3920.45	5610.41	3920.45	0.20	0.67	1.86
56.5	22	2428.24	3902.40	5591.54	3902.40	0.21	0.67	1.85
57	17	2411.46	3884.70	5573.31	3884.70	0.21	0.67	1.85
57.5	20	2395.10	3867.81	5556.35	3867.81	0.21	0.67	1.85
58	26	2379.43	3852.15	5541.31	3852.15	0.21	0.67	1.85
58.5	28	2364.69	3838.16	5528.81	3838.16	0.21	0.67	1.85
59	17	2351.14	3826.24	5519.45	3826.24	0.21	0.67	1.85
59.5	29	2338.75	3816.39	5513.25	3816.39	0.21	0.67	1.84
60	18	2327.28	3808.24	5509.68	3808.24	0.21	0.67	1.84
60.5	20	2316.49	3801.40	5508.21	3801.40	0.21	0.67	1.84
61	26	2306.13	3795.48	5508.29	3795.48	0.21	0.67	1.84
61.5	24	2295.97	3790.12	5509.39	3790.12	0.21	0.67	1.84
62	19	2285.76	3784.92	5510.97	3784.92	0.22	0.67	1.84
62.5	31	2275.27	3779.53	5512.5	3779.53	0.22	0.67	1.84
63	30	2264.28	3773.56	5513.43	3773.56	0.22	0.67	1.83
63.5	15	2252.57	3766.64	5513.22	3766.64	0.22	0.67	1.83
64	32	2239.91	3758.41	5511.35	3758.41	0.22	0.68	1.83
64.5	18	2226.11	3748.52	5507.31	3748.52	0.22	0.68	1.83
65	26	2211.10	3736.87	5500.92	3736.87	0.22	0.68	1.83
65.5	17	2194.89	3723.46	5492.20	3723.46	0.22	0.68	1.83
66	13	2177.51	3708.31	5481.17	3708.31	0.23	0.68	1.83
66.5	23	2158.97	3691.44	5467.85	3691.44	0.23	0.68	1.82
67	18	2139.29	3672.88	5452.26	3672.88	0.23	0.68	1.82
67.5	17	2118.5	3652.64	5434.44	3652.64	0.23	0.68	1.82

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
68	21	2096.6	3630.75	5414.42	3630.75	0.23	0.68	1.82
68.5	16	2073.64	3607.25	5392.22	3607.25	0.23	0.68	1.82
69	15	2049.63	3582.15	5367.89	3582.15	0.23	0.68	1.82
69.5	23	2024.61	3555.5	5341.46	3555.50	0.24	0.68	1.82
70	26	1998.61	3527.37	5313.03	3527.37	0.24	0.68	1.81
70.5	24	1971.77	3497.96	5282.93	3497.96	0.24	0.67	1.81
71	18	1944.27	3467.57	5251.56	3467.57	0.24	0.67	1.81
71.5	13	1916.23	3436.44	5219.31	3436.44	0.24	0.67	1.81
72	27	1887.82	3404.84	5186.57	3404.84	0.25	0.67	1.81
72.5	24	1859.16	3373.00	5153.72	3373.00	0.25	0.67	1.81
73	25	1830.39	3341.17	5121.13	3341.17	0.25	0.67	1.81
73.5	23	1801.63	3309.57	5089.15	3309.57	0.25	0.67	1.80
74	22	1772.99	3278.43	5058.15	3278.43	0.25	0.67	1.80
74.5	10	1744.57	3247.96	5028.46	3247.96	0.26	0.67	1.80
75	17	1716.48	3218.36	5000.42	3218.36	0.26	0.67	1.80
75.5	7	1688.77	3189.77	4974.29	3189.77	0.26	0.67	1.80
76	9	1661.42	3162.16	4950.05	3162.16	0.26	0.67	1.80
76.5	9	1634.38	3135.50	4927.66	3135.50	0.27	0.67	1.80
77	13	1607.61	3109.72	4907.07	3109.72	0.27	0.67	1.79
77.5	9	1581.07	3084.78	4888.25	3084.78	0.27	0.67	1.79
78	2	1554.72	3060.64	4871.16	3060.64	0.27	0.67	1.79
78.5	9	1528.51	3037.25	4855.76	3037.25	0.28	0.67	1.79
79	3	1502.41	3014.57	4842.03	3014.56	0.28	0.67	1.79
79.5	9	1476.37	2992.55	4829.94	2992.54	0.28	0.67	1.79
80	1	1450.26	2970.94	4819.12	2970.94	0.29	0.66	1.79

3B: Females who were not taking CDs or HRT

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
0.25	51	932.37	1781.19	2871.35	1781.19	0.27	0.55	1.67
0.5	102	969.16	1835.34	2948.63	1835.34	0.27	0.54	1.67
0.75	19	1006.78	1890.59	3027.37	1890.59	0.27	0.53	1.67
1	66	1045.22	1946.92	3107.53	1946.92	0.26	0.53	1.67
1.5	21	1124.45	2062.62	3271.81	2062.62	0.26	0.52	1.67
2	41	1206.65	2182.09	3440.92	2182.09	0.26	0.50	1.67
2.5	45	1291.55	2304.88	3614.16	2304.88	0.25	0.49	1.67
3	41	1378.81	2430.42	3790.70	2430.42	0.25	0.48	1.67
3.5	37	1468.03	2558.08	3969.61	2558.08	0.24	0.47	1.68
4	42	1558.72	2687.11	4149.77	2687.11	0.24	0.46	1.68
4.5	50	1650.33	2816.66	4329.98	2816.66	0.24	0.45	1.68
5	55	1742.23	2945.79	4508.87	2945.79	0.23	0.44	1.68
5.5	46	1833.89	3073.72	4685.35	3073.72	0.23	0.43	1.68
6	58	1924.89	3199.92	4858.74	3199.92	0.23	0.43	1.68
6.5	52	2014.85	3323.87	5028.36	3323.87	0.23	0.42	1.68
7	71	2103.37	3445.09	5193.58	3445.09	0.22	0.41	1.68
7.5	42	2190.09	3563.09	5353.77	3563.09	0.22	0.40	1.68
8	67	2274.62	3677.42	5508.36	3677.42	0.22	0.39	1.68
8.5	53	2356.63	3787.63	5656.78	3787.63	0.22	0.38	1.68
9	66	2435.79	3893.31	5798.52	3893.31	0.21	0.38	1.68
9.5	51	2511.77	3994.08	5933.10	3994.08	0.21	0.37	1.68
10	74	2584.29	4089.60	6060.10	4089.60	0.21	0.36	1.68
10.5	53	2653.08	4179.55	6179.12	4179.55	0.21	0.36	1.68
11	74	2717.91	4263.64	6289.82	4263.64	0.21	0.35	1.68
11.5	52	2778.54	4341.59	6391.85	4341.59	0.21	0.34	1.68
12	78	2834.77	4413.17	6484.94	4413.17	0.21	0.34	1.68
12.5	61	2886.44	4478.20	6568.86	4478.20	0.20	0.33	1.69
13	74	2933.39	4536.51	6643.43	4536.51	0.20	0.33	1.69
13.5	61	2975.52	4588.00	6708.53	4588.00	0.20	0.32	1.69
14	72	3012.75	4632.57	6764.07	4632.57	0.20	0.32	1.69
14.5	69	3045.02	4670.19	6810.02	4670.19	0.20	0.31	1.69
15	52	3072.31	4700.86	6846.40	4700.86	0.20	0.31	1.69
15.5	51	3094.62	4724.61	6873.28	4724.61	0.20	0.30	1.69
16	36	3111.99	4741.52	6890.80	4741.52	0.20	0.30	1.69
16.5	37	3124.63	4751.92	6899.42	4751.92	0.20	0.30	1.69
17	24	3132.81	4756.25	6899.79	4756.25	0.20	0.29	1.69
17.5	15	3136.87	4754.98	6892.59	4754.98	0.20	0.29	1.69
18	11	3137.11	4748.60	6878.53	4748.60	0.20	0.29	1.69
18.5	8	3133.89	4737.63	6858.32	4737.63	0.19	0.28	1.69
19	2	3127.55	4722.57	6832.70	4722.57	0.19	0.28	1.69
19.5	2	3118.45	4703.95	6802.40	4703.95	0.19	0.28	1.69
20	4	3106.96	4682.29	6768.15	4682.29	0.19	0.28	1.69
20.5	13	3093.43	4658.10	6730.69	4658.10	0.19	0.27	1.69
21	42	3078.21	4631.91	6690.71	4631.91	0.19	0.27	1.69
21.5	27	3061.66	4604.20	6648.91	4604.20	0.19	0.27	1.70
22	23	3044.01	4575.30	6605.76	4575.30	0.19	0.27	1.70

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
22.5	21	3025.50	4545.54	6561.67	4545.54	0.19	0.27	1.70
23	13	3006.32	4515.20	6517.05	4515.20	0.19	0.27	1.70
23.5	15	2986.70	4484.57	6472.28	4484.57	0.19	0.27	1.70
24	8	2966.83	4453.94	6427.76	4453.94	0.19	0.26	1.70
24.5	6	2946.91	4423.58	6383.86	4423.58	0.19	0.26	1.70
25	7	2927.15	4393.75	6340.93	4393.75	0.19	0.26	1.70
25.5	6	2907.71	4364.71	6299.33	4364.71	0.19	0.26	1.70
26	12	2888.79	4336.72	6259.40	4336.72	0.19	0.26	1.70
26.5	5	2870.56	4310.01	6221.48	4310.01	0.19	0.26	1.70
27	6	2853.18	4284.82	6185.87	4284.82	0.19	0.26	1.70
27.5	5	2836.79	4261.33	6152.84	4261.33	0.19	0.26	1.70
28	14	2821.52	4239.71	6122.62	4239.71	0.19	0.27	1.70
28.5	10	2807.49	4220.16	6095.46	4220.16	0.19	0.27	1.70
29	9	2794.82	4202.82	6071.59	4202.82	0.19	0.27	1.70
29.5	9	2783.64	4187.89	6051.25	4187.89	0.19	0.27	1.70
30	9	2774.08	4175.54	6034.67	4175.54	0.19	0.27	1.71
30.5	5	2766.24	4165.93	6022.12	4165.93	0.19	0.27	1.71
31	5	2760.27	4159.26	6013.83	4159.26	0.19	0.27	1.71
31.5	5	2756.27	4155.69	6010.07	4155.69	0.19	0.27	1.71
32	3	2754.38	4155.43	6011.09	4155.43	0.19	0.28	1.71
32.5	1	2754.55	4158.39	6016.78	4158.39	0.19	0.28	1.71
33	5	2756.38	4163.96	6026.24	4163.96	0.19	0.28	1.71
33.5	5	2759.40	4171.44	6038.48	4171.44	0.20	0.28	1.71
34	8	2763.18	4180.16	6052.48	4180.16	0.20	0.29	1.71
34.5	0	2767.25	4189.43	6067.25	4189.43	0.20	0.29	1.71
35	7	2771.17	4198.55	6081.77	4198.55	0.20	0.29	1.71
35.5	2	2774.47	4206.81	6095.02	4206.81	0.20	0.29	1.71
36	6	2776.69	4213.51	6105.95	4213.51	0.20	0.30	1.71
36.5	2	2777.38	4217.94	6113.54	4217.94	0.20	0.30	1.71
37	4	2776.07	4219.39	6116.73	4219.39	0.20	0.30	1.71
37.5	1	2772.31	4217.15	6114.53	4217.15	0.20	0.31	1.71
38	9	2765.96	4211.01	6106.57	4211.01	0.20	0.31	1.71
38.5	3	2757.29	4201.35	6093.43	4201.35	0.20	0.31	1.72
39	6	2746.60	4188.61	6075.74	4188.61	0.20	0.32	1.72
39.5	5	2734.19	4173.25	6054.15	4173.25	0.20	0.32	1.72
40	1	2720.35	4155.69	6029.28	4155.69	0.20	0.33	1.72
40.5	10	2705.39	4136.39	6001.78	4136.39	0.20	0.33	1.72
41	29	2689.58	4115.78	5972.27	4115.78	0.20	0.34	1.72
41.5	27	2673.22	4094.29	5941.39	4094.29	0.20	0.34	1.72
42	33	2656.59	4072.33	5909.73	4072.33	0.20	0.34	1.72
42.5	29	2639.94	4050.32	5877.89	4050.32	0.20	0.35	1.72
43	38	2623.55	4028.65	5846.45	4028.65	0.20	0.35	1.72
43.5	36	2607.62	4007.65	5815.87	4007.65	0.20	0.36	1.72
44	33	2592.28	3987.52	5786.47	3987.52	0.20	0.36	1.72
44.5	29	2577.70	3968.51	5758.59	3968.51	0.20	0.37	1.72
45	34	2564.01	3950.82	5732.54	3950.82	0.20	0.37	1.72
45.5	25	2551.35	3934.68	5708.64	3934.68	0.20	0.38	1.72
46	27	2539.85	3920.29	5687.21	3920.29	0.20	0.38	1.72

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
46.5	22	2529.65	3907.88	5668.55	3907.88	0.20	0.39	1.73
47	25	2520.89	3897.65	5652.97	3897.65	0.20	0.39	1.73
47.5	31	2513.69	3889.82	5640.79	3889.82	0.20	0.40	1.73
48	22	2508.19	3884.60	5632.32	3884.60	0.20	0.40	1.73
48.5	23	2504.51	3882.18	5627.84	3882.18	0.20	0.41	1.73
49	32	2502.57	3882.45	5627.19	3882.45	0.20	0.42	1.73
49.5	23	2502.18	3885.11	5629.94	3885.11	0.20	0.42	1.73
50	36	2503.14	3889.89	5635.68	3889.89	0.20	0.43	1.73
50.5	21	2505.26	3896.48	5644.00	3896.48	0.20	0.43	1.73
51	30	2508.36	3904.61	5654.49	3904.61	0.20	0.44	1.73
51.5	16	2512.24	3913.99	5666.73	3913.99	0.20	0.45	1.73
52	30	2516.72	3924.32	5680.30	3924.32	0.20	0.45	1.73
52.5	28	2521.59	3935.31	5694.80	3935.31	0.20	0.46	1.73
53	25	2526.68	3946.67	5709.79	3946.67	0.20	0.46	1.73
53.5	24	2531.78	3958.11	5724.86	3958.11	0.20	0.47	1.73
54	22	2536.70	3969.32	5739.59	3969.32	0.20	0.48	1.73
54.5	18	2541.31	3980.11	5753.70	3980.11	0.20	0.48	1.74
55	22	2545.50	3990.31	5766.94	3990.31	0.20	0.49	1.74
55.5	21	2549.16	3999.74	5779.09	3999.74	0.20	0.50	1.74
56	28	2552.16	4008.24	5789.91	4008.24	0.20	0.50	1.74
56.5	19	2554.41	4015.63	5799.15	4015.63	0.20	0.51	1.74
57	14	2555.77	4021.74	5806.58	4021.74	0.20	0.52	1.74
57.5	18	2556.15	4026.40	5811.95	4026.40	0.20	0.52	1.74
58	18	2555.42	4029.42	5815.02	4029.42	0.20	0.53	1.74
58.5	21	2553.47	4030.64	5815.57	4030.64	0.20	0.53	1.74
59	18	2550.19	4029.89	5813.36	4029.89	0.20	0.54	1.74
59.5	18	2545.52	4027.07	5808.25	4027.07	0.20	0.55	1.74
60	14	2539.54	4022.34	5800.48	4022.34	0.20	0.55	1.74
60.5	23	2532.40	4015.90	5790.39	4015.90	0.20	0.56	1.74
61	27	2524.23	4007.99	5778.30	4007.99	0.20	0.57	1.74
61.5	25	2515.15	3998.82	5764.53	3998.82	0.20	0.57	1.74
62	25	2505.31	3988.61	5749.43	3988.61	0.20	0.58	1.74
62.5	30	2494.84	3977.58	5733.31	3977.58	0.20	0.59	1.75
63	27	2483.86	3965.95	5716.50	3965.95	0.20	0.60	1.75
63.5	29	2472.49	3953.92	5699.31	3953.92	0.20	0.60	1.75
64	21	2460.87	3941.72	5682.07	3941.72	0.21	0.61	1.75
64.5	17	2449.11	3929.54	5665.08	3929.54	0.21	0.62	1.75
65	13	2437.28	3917.51	5648.54	3917.51	0.21	0.62	1.75
65.5	11	2425.30	3905.54	5632.32	3905.54	0.21	0.63	1.75
66	19	2413.11	3893.52	5616.29	3893.52	0.21	0.64	1.75
66.5	20	2400.62	3881.33	5600.28	3881.33	0.21	0.64	1.75
67	18	2387.74	3868.86	5584.15	3868.86	0.21	0.65	1.75
67.5	12	2374.40	3856.01	5567.76	3856.01	0.21	0.66	1.75
68	15	2360.52	3842.65	5550.96	3842.65	0.21	0.66	1.75
68.5	30	2346.02	3828.69	5533.60	3828.69	0.21	0.67	1.75
69	23	2330.82	3814.01	5515.54	3814.01	0.21	0.68	1.75
69.5	15	2314.86	3798.52	5496.66	3798.52	0.21	0.68	1.75
70	17	2298.06	3782.10	5476.81	3782.10	0.21	0.69	1.75

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
70.5	15	2280.39	3764.74	5455.96	3764.74	0.21	0.70	1.76
71	16	2261.88	3746.49	5434.23	3746.49	0.21	0.70	1.76
71.5	22	2242.57	3727.43	5411.73	3727.43	0.21	0.71	1.76
72	20	2222.50	3707.64	5388.60	3707.64	0.22	0.71	1.76
72.5	16	2201.69	3687.20	5364.96	3687.20	0.22	0.72	1.76
73	18	2180.19	3666.19	5340.92	3666.19	0.22	0.73	1.76
73.5	17	2158.01	3644.66	5316.62	3644.66	0.22	0.73	1.76
74	14	2135.20	3622.71	5292.17	3622.71	0.22	0.74	1.76
74.5	11	2111.78	3600.39	5267.69	3600.39	0.22	0.75	1.76
75	16	2087.76	3577.78	5243.31	3577.78	0.22	0.75	1.76
75.5	7	2063.18	3554.94	5219.14	3554.94	0.22	0.76	1.76
76	6	2038.05	3531.94	5195.27	3531.94	0.23	0.76	1.76
76.5	11	2012.37	3508.81	5171.81	3508.81	0.23	0.77	1.76
77	7	1986.15	3485.60	5148.83	3485.60	0.23	0.78	1.76
77.5	7	1959.39	3462.36	5126.42	3462.36	0.23	0.78	1.76
78	8	1932.08	3439.11	5104.67	3439.11	0.23	0.79	1.77
78.5	10	1904.22	3415.91	5083.66	3415.91	0.23	0.79	1.77
79	9	1875.81	3392.79	5063.48	3392.79	0.24	0.80	1.77
79.5	3	1846.84	3369.78	5044.21	3369.78	0.24	0.81	1.77
80	3	1817.28	3346.93	5025.96	3346.93	0.24	0.81	1.77

3C: Females who were taking or not taking CDs or HRT

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
0.25	51	941.47	1792.09	2848.31	1792.09	0.27	0.60	1.74
0.5	102	978.80	1845.92	2924.05	1845.92	0.26	0.59	1.74
0.75	19	1016.89	1900.84	3001.36	1900.84	0.26	0.59	1.74
1	66	1055.74	1956.82	3080.21	1956.82	0.26	0.58	1.74
1.5	21	1135.61	2071.77	3242.23	2071.77	0.26	0.57	1.74
2	41	1218.15	2190.39	3409.56	2190.39	0.25	0.55	1.73
2.5	45	1303.05	2312.19	3581.53	2312.19	0.25	0.54	1.73
3	41	1389.95	2436.58	3757.31	2436.58	0.24	0.52	1.73
3.5	37	1478.38	2562.87	3935.94	2562.87	0.24	0.51	1.73
4	42	1567.82	2690.27	4116.32	2690.27	0.24	0.50	1.73
4.5	50	1657.66	2817.88	4297.18	2817.88	0.23	0.48	1.73
5	55	1747.25	2944.71	4477.14	2944.71	0.23	0.47	1.73
5.5	46	1836.03	3069.99	4655.17	3069.99	0.23	0.46	1.73
6	58	1923.66	3193.30	4830.75	3193.3	0.23	0.44	1.72
6.5	52	2009.83	3314.26	5003.43	3314.26	0.23	0.43	1.72
7	71	2094.26	3432.55	5172.82	3432.55	0.22	0.41	1.72
7.5	42	2176.69	3547.85	5338.56	3547.85	0.22	0.40	1.72
8	67	2256.88	3659.89	5500.32	3659.89	0.22	0.39	1.72
8.5	53	2334.63	3768.45	5657.85	3768.45	0.22	0.37	1.72
9	66	2409.78	3873.34	5810.94	3873.34	0.22	0.36	1.72
9.5	51	2482.18	3974.41	5959.42	3974.41	0.22	0.34	1.72
10	74	2551.72	4071.56	6103.19	4071.56	0.22	0.33	1.72
10.5	53	2618.34	4164.71	6242.18	4164.71	0.22	0.32	1.71
11	74	2681.88	4253.68	6376.14	4253.68	0.22	0.30	1.71
11.5	52	2742.14	4338.19	6504.66	4338.19	0.21	0.29	1.71
12	78	2798.95	4417.98	6627.39	4417.98	0.21	0.27	1.71
12.5	61	2852.13	4492.82	6743.97	4492.82	0.21	0.26	1.71
13	74	2901.55	4562.48	6854.05	4562.48	0.21	0.25	1.71
13.5	61	2947.07	4626.78	6957.33	4626.78	0.21	0.23	1.71
14	72	2988.58	4685.53	7053.53	4685.53	0.21	0.22	1.71
14.5	72	3025.99	4738.60	7142.38	4738.60	0.21	0.21	1.70
15	56	3059.23	4785.85	7223.65	4785.85	0.21	0.19	1.70
15.5	58	3088.24	4827.20	7297.13	4827.20	0.21	0.18	1.70
16	45	3112.99	4862.57	7362.67	4862.57	0.21	0.17	1.70
16.5	48	3133.57	4892.05	7420.34	4892.05	0.22	0.16	1.70
17	33	3150.11	4915.83	7470.32	4915.83	0.22	0.14	1.70
17.5	22	3162.74	4934.11	7512.83	4934.11	0.22	0.13	1.70
18	22	3171.65	4947.10	7548.14	4947.10	0.22	0.12	1.70
18.5	18	3177.01	4955.06	7576.52	4955.06	0.22	0.10	1.69
19	5	3179.03	4958.26	7598.30	4958.26	0.22	0.09	1.69
19.5	4	3177.89	4956.96	7613.80	4956.96	0.22	0.08	1.69
20	9	3173.83	4951.46	7623.37	4951.46	0.22	0.07	1.69
20.5	24	3167.05	4942.06	7627.38	4942.06	0.22	0.06	1.69
21	70	3157.78	4929.07	7626.21	4929.07	0.22	0.05	1.69
21.5	48	3146.26	4912.81	7620.27	4912.81	0.22	0.03	1.69
22	50	3132.77	4893.70	7610.12	4893.7	0.22	0.02	1.69

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
22.5	35	3117.63	4872.19	7596.34	4872.19	0.22	0.01	1.69
23	23	3101.14	4848.69	7579.54	4848.69	0.22	0.00	1.68
23.5	25	3083.58	4823.65	7560.31	4823.65	0.22	-0.01	1.68
24	16	3065.26	4797.48	7539.23	4797.48	0.22	-0.02	1.68
24.5	11	3046.46	4770.61	7516.9	4770.61	0.23	-0.03	1.68
25	13	3027.45	4743.44	7493.88	4743.44	0.23	-0.04	1.68
25.5	9	3008.50	4716.36	7470.75	4716.36	0.23	-0.05	1.68
26	21	2989.87	4689.76	7448.07	4689.76	0.23	-0.06	1.68
26.5	11	2971.83	4664.03	7426.39	4664.03	0.23	-0.07	1.68
27	10	2954.58	4639.47	7406.18	4639.47	0.23	-0.08	1.68
27.5	7	2938.19	4616.19	7387.55	4616.19	0.23	-0.09	1.67
28	21	2922.73	4594.27	7370.61	4594.27	0.23	-0.10	1.67
28.5	16	2908.26	4573.78	7355.42	4573.78	0.23	-0.10	1.67
29	12	2894.81	4554.78	7342.07	4554.78	0.23	-0.11	1.67
29.5	13	2882.45	4537.36	7330.63	4537.36	0.23	-0.12	1.67
30	15	2871.23	4521.57	7321.19	4521.57	0.23	-0.13	1.67
30.5	8	2861.19	4507.50	7313.83	4507.50	0.23	-0.13	1.67
31	10	2852.39	4495.21	7308.64	4495.21	0.23	-0.14	1.67
31.5	5	2844.88	4484.77	7305.70	4484.77	0.23	-0.15	1.66
32	7	2838.70	4476.25	7305.10	4476.25	0.24	-0.15	1.66
32.5	2	2833.82	4469.58	7306.69	4469.58	0.24	-0.16	1.66
33	9	2829.96	4464.34	7309.75	4464.34	0.24	-0.17	1.66
33.5	6	2826.86	4460.10	7313.56	4460.10	0.24	-0.17	1.66
34	11	2824.26	4456.42	7317.35	4456.42	0.24	-0.18	1.66
34.5	1	2821.86	4452.86	7320.37	4452.86	0.24	-0.18	1.66
35	8	2819.40	4448.99	7321.88	4448.99	0.24	-0.18	1.66
35.5	2	2816.61	4444.38	7321.13	4444.38	0.24	-0.19	1.66
36	9	2813.21	4438.60	7317.38	4438.60	0.24	-0.19	1.65
36.5	2	2808.94	4431.22	7309.90	4431.22	0.24	-0.20	1.65
37	7	2803.53	4421.81	7297.95	4421.81	0.24	-0.20	1.65
37.5	3	2796.70	4409.97	7280.85	4409.97	0.24	-0.20	1.65
38	11	2788.42	4395.62	7258.47	4395.62	0.24	-0.20	1.65
38.5	4	2778.91	4379.12	7231.38	4379.12	0.24	-0.20	1.65
39	7	2768.40	4360.86	7200.24	4360.86	0.24	-0.21	1.65
39.5	6	2757.15	4341.22	7165.70	4341.22	0.24	-0.21	1.65
40	3	2745.38	4320.59	7128.40	4320.59	0.24	-0.21	1.65
40.5	15	2733.32	4299.34	7088.98	4299.34	0.24	-0.21	1.64
41	41	2721.21	4277.83	7048.08	4277.83	0.24	-0.21	1.64
41.5	31	2709.27	4256.43	7006.31	4256.43	0.24	-0.21	1.64
42	44	2697.72	4235.49	6964.29	4235.49	0.24	-0.21	1.64
42.5	37	2686.76	4215.35	6922.61	4215.35	0.23	-0.20	1.64
43	56	2676.61	4196.34	6881.85	4196.34	0.23	-0.20	1.64
43.5	44	2667.31	4178.56	6842.19	4178.56	0.23	-0.20	1.64
44	47	2658.79	4161.88	6803.49	4161.88	0.23	-0.20	1.64
44.5	34	2650.97	4146.21	6765.6	4146.21	0.23	-0.19	1.64
45	49	2643.78	4131.42	6728.36	4131.42	0.23	-0.19	1.63
45.5	36	2637.13	4117.41	6691.65	4117.41	0.23	-0.19	1.63
46	37	2630.95	4104.07	6655.32	4104.07	0.23	-0.18	1.63

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
46.5	28	2625.16	4091.28	6619.25	4091.28	0.23	-0.18	1.63
47	32	2619.69	4078.95	6583.30	4078.95	0.23	-0.17	1.63
47.5	40	2614.45	4066.97	6547.37	4066.97	0.23	-0.16	1.63
48	35	2609.38	4055.24	6511.33	4055.24	0.23	-0.16	1.63
48.5	39	2604.40	4043.66	6475.09	4043.66	0.23	-0.15	1.63
49	40	2599.56	4032.31	6438.81	4032.31	0.22	-0.14	1.63
49.5	35	2594.93	4021.34	6402.8	4021.34	0.22	-0.13	1.62
50	52	2590.61	4010.9	6367.34	4010.9	0.22	-0.12	1.62
50.5	29	2586.68	4001.16	6332.73	4001.16	0.22	-0.11	1.62
51	36	2583.24	3992.26	6299.25	3992.26	0.22	-0.10	1.62
51.5	18	2580.37	3984.35	6267.18	3984.35	0.22	-0.09	1.62
52	34	2578.15	3977.59	6236.80	3977.59	0.22	-0.08	1.62
52.5	33	2576.68	3972.13	6208.37	3972.13	0.22	-0.07	1.62
53	31	2576.04	3968.11	6182.15	3968.11	0.22	-0.06	1.62
53.5	31	2576.3	3965.69	6158.41	3965.69	0.22	-0.05	1.62
54	23	2577.53	3964.96	6137.32	3964.96	0.22	-0.03	1.61
54.5	20	2579.57	3965.73	6118.6	3965.73	0.21	-0.02	1.61
55	25	2582.2	3967.68	6101.77	3967.68	0.21	0.00	1.61
55.5	23	2585.2	3970.48	6086.37	3970.48	0.21	0.01	1.61
56	31	2588.34	3973.81	6071.94	3973.81	0.21	0.03	1.61
56.5	20	2591.37	3977.35	6058.01	3977.35	0.21	0.04	1.61
57	15	2594.08	3980.79	6044.15	3980.79	0.21	0.06	1.61
57.5	20	2596.23	3983.78	6029.89	3983.78	0.21	0.08	1.61
58	22	2597.57	3986.01	6014.79	3986.01	0.21	0.10	1.61
58.5	24	2597.88	3987.14	5998.41	3987.14	0.21	0.11	1.60
59	19	2596.9	3986.86	5980.30	3986.86	0.21	0.13	1.60
59.5	18	2594.47	3984.93	5960.17	3984.93	0.21	0.15	1.60
60	15	2590.59	3981.42	5938.19	3981.42	0.21	0.17	1.60
60.5	24	2585.36	3976.5	5914.66	3976.5	0.20	0.20	1.60
61	30	2578.85	3970.34	5889.86	3970.34	0.20	0.22	1.60
61.5	27	2571.14	3963.10	5864.08	3963.1	0.20	0.24	1.60
62	25	2562.29	3954.94	5837.61	3954.94	0.20	0.26	1.60
62.5	30	2552.39	3946.02	5810.71	3946.02	0.20	0.29	1.60
63	31	2541.49	3936.52	5783.67	3936.52	0.20	0.31	1.60
63.5	30	2529.68	3926.59	5756.73	3926.59	0.20	0.34	1.59
64	23	2516.99	3916.39	5730.17	3916.39	0.20	0.36	1.59
64.5	18	2503.49	3906.08	5704.24	3906.08	0.20	0.39	1.59
65	15	2489.19	3895.75	5679.08	3895.75	0.20	0.42	1.59
65.5	12	2473.99	3885.33	5654.63	3885.33	0.20	0.45	1.59
66	19	2457.78	3874.74	5630.78	3874.74	0.20	0.48	1.59
66.5	22	2440.42	3863.88	5607.40	3863.88	0.20	0.51	1.59
67	19	2421.81	3852.66	5584.41	3852.66	0.20	0.54	1.59
67.5	12	2401.80	3841.01	5561.68	3841.01	0.20	0.57	1.59
68	16	2380.26	3828.82	5539.11	3828.82	0.20	0.60	1.58
68.5	31	2357.06	3816.02	5516.61	3816.02	0.21	0.63	1.58
69	27	2332.04	3802.52	5494.07	3802.52	0.21	0.67	1.58
69.5	18	2305.04	3788.24	5471.39	3788.24	0.21	0.70	1.58
70	18	2275.91	3773.09	5448.47	3773.09	0.21	0.74	1.58

Age [years]	n	2.5th perc	50.0th perc	97.5th perc	mu	sigma	nu	tau
70.5	17	2244.49	3757.05	5425.28	3757.05	0.21	0.77	1.58
71	18	2210.66	3740.15	5401.90	3740.15	0.21	0.81	1.58
71.5	25	2174.28	3722.43	5378.40	3722.43	0.21	0.85	1.58
72	21	2135.22	3703.94	5354.86	3703.94	0.22	0.89	1.58
72.5	16	2093.32	3684.72	5331.37	3684.71	0.22	0.92	1.58
73	20	2048.41	3664.82	5307.99	3664.79	0.22	0.96	1.57
73.5	18	2000.35	3644.29	5284.82	3644.23	0.22	1.01	1.57
74	14	1949.03	3623.17	5261.93	3623.06	0.23	1.05	1.57
74.5	11	1894.40	3601.54	5239.4	3601.32	0.23	1.09	1.57
75	17	1836.51	3579.45	5217.33	3579.06	0.23	1.13	1.57
75.5	7	1775.58	3556.98	5195.8	3556.33	0.24	1.18	1.57
76	6	1712.01	3534.23	5174.93	3533.17	0.24	1.22	1.57
76.5	12	1646.43	3511.35	5154.87	3509.65	0.24	1.27	1.57
77	7	1579.74	3488.46	5135.75	3485.86	0.25	1.31	1.57
77.5	7	1513.05	3465.73	5117.74	3461.84	0.26	1.36	1.56
78	8	1447.62	3443.34	5100.98	3437.68	0.26	1.41	1.56
78.5	10	1384.8	3421.49	5085.64	3413.43	0.27	1.46	1.56
79	9	1325.84	3400.37	5071.87	3389.15	0.27	1.51	1.56
79.5	3	1271.84	3380.22	5059.83	3364.92	0.28	1.56	1.56
80	5	1223.6	3361.26	5049.69	3340.79	0.29	1.61	1.56

Suppl. Table 4: Age distribution of non-obese girls (BMI ± 1.881 SDS) and females (BMI 18 to <30 kg/m²) with reported use of contraceptive drugs (CDs) or hormone replacement therapy (HRT) who were excluded from and compared with the reference cohort. CD use included estrogen- and progestin-based components (epCDs, 14.5–64.4 years) or only progestin-based components (pCDs, 31.0–55.8 years); HRT use included estrogen-based or combined estrogen-progestin-based components (e/epHRT, 41.5–76.1 years). The portion of the respective age range related to the total number of females is given as a percentage. Abbreviation: “n.a.”, not available for the specific age range.

		epCDs	pCDs	e/ep HRT
Girls	n	63 (74)		
	BMI SDS	0.13 $\pm$ 0.86 (–1.58 to 1.85)	n.a.	n.a.
	Age range [years]			
	14-18	74 (19.6%)	n.a.	n.a.
Females	n	423	34	91
	BMI [kg/m ²]	22.58 $\pm$ 2.61 (18.03 to 29.87)	24.56 $\pm$ 2.90 (18.95 to 29.41)	24.22 $\pm$ 2.66 (18.72 to 29.37)
	Age range [years]			
	19-29	195 (42.3%)	n.a.	n.a.
	30-39	36 (29.5%)	2 (1.6%)	n.a.
	40-49	174 (22.5%)	23 (3.0%)	12 (1.6%)
	50-59	17 (3.5%)	9 (1.8%)	36 (7.4%)
	60-69	1 (0.2%)	n.a.	29 (6.5%)
	70-76	n.a.	n.a.	14 (5.6%)

Suppl. Table 5: Effect of oral vs. non-oral intake of combined estrogen-progestin-based CDs (epCDs) or progestin-based CDs (pCDs) as well as of estrogen- or combined estrogen-progestin-based HRT (e/epHRT) on IGF-I SDS and IGFBP-3 SDS in adult females (≥ 19 years). The beta estimate (β) and the corresponding 95% confidence interval (CI) are presented.

Drugs	Parameter	Oral application			Non-oral application		
		n	β (95%CI)	p	n	β (95%CI)	p
epCD	IGF-I SDS	395	-0.43 (-0.54; -0.32)	<0.001	28	-0.24 (-0.63; 0.14)	0.216
	IGFBP-3 SDS		1.13 (1.01; 1.25)	<0.001		0.56 (0.13; 1.00)	<0.05
pCD	IGF-I SDS	26	0.88 (0.48; 1.28)	<0.001	8	0.59 (-0.13; 1.31)	0.106
	IGFBP-3 SDS		-0.35 (-0.80; 0.10)	0.129		-0.42 (-1.21; 0.39)	0.315
HRT	IGF-I SDS	51	0.02 (-0.26; 0.31)	0.878	40	-0.05 (0.38; 0.27)	0.743
	IGFBP-3 SDS		-0.16 (-0.47; 0.14)	0.288		-0.29 (-0.63; 0.05)	0.095

Suppl. Table 6: Mean and standard deviation (SD) values for IGF-I and IGFBP-3 as well as the corresponding SDS values for the ECLIA assay and the CLIA assay. Median, range, mean and SD values for the difference between ECLIA and CLIA are also presented. Included are n = 3476 samples from n = 2050 subjects, with a mean age of 10.7 ± 5.6 years (range: 0.2 to 40.6 years, subjects ≥18 years: n = 249, 23.2 ± 3.7 years); “n.c.”, not calculated.

	ECLIA	CLIA	Δ (ECLIA–CLIA)		
	Mean ± SD [ng/mL]	Mean ± SD [ng/mL]	Median, (range) [ng/mL]	Mean ± SD [ng/mL]	Mean [%]
IGF-I	200.5 ± 118.3	209.1 ± 120.8	–6.4 (–245.5 to 294.8)	–8.6 ± 22.3	4.3
IGFBP-3	3816.5 ± 1199.7	4266.6 ± 1081.7	–423.5 (–3450 to 3650)	–450.1 ± 579.8	11.8
IGF-I SDS	–0.05 ± 1.04	–0.22 ± 0.97	0.14 (–2.55 to 3.61)	0.17 ± 0.72	n.c.
IGFBP-3 SDS	–0.04 ± 0.99	0.36 ± 0.85	–0.37 (–4.08 to 3.66)	–0.40 ± 0.75	n.c.

Suppl. Table 7: Differences in IGF-I SDS and IGFBP-3 SDS that were >3, 2 to 3, or 1 to 2 SDS when comparing the values of the ECLIA and the CLIA assays after measurement and after assay-specific, sex- and age-adjusted SDS calculation. The percentage (in parentheses) is based on the total number of comparison for the cohort (n = 2050 subjects with 3476 samples).

Difference (Δ) between ECLIA and CLIA	IGF-I SDS	IGFBP-3 SDS
>3 SDS	1 (0.03%)	15 (0.4%)
2 to 3 SDS	13 (0.4%)	79 (2.3%)
1 to 2 SDS	597 (17.2%)	640 (18.4%)
>1 SDS	611 (17.6%)	734 (21.1%)

Suppl. Table 8: Detailed information about inclusion and exclusion criteria for children and adults corresponding to Figure 1. All criteria were applied to the reference cohort (age <19 years: BMI $\pm$ 1.881 SDS (>-1.881 to 1.881), age $\geq$ 19 years: BMI >18 to 30) and to the obese cohort (age <19 years: BMI >1.881 SDS, age $\geq$ 19 years: BMI >30).

Children and Adolescents (0 to <19 years)	Adults (19 to <81 years)
Cohorts: LIFE Child study, LIFE Adult study	Cohorts: LIFE Child study, LIFE Adult study, student cohort, BRC cohort
(A) Inclusion criteria	
Data available for age and BMI	
Reference cohort: BMI $\pm$ 1.881 SDS Obese cohort: BMI >1.881 SDS	Reference cohort: BMI: >18 to 30 kg/m ² Obese cohort: BMI >30 kg/m ²
(B) Exclusion criteria	
(B.1) General criteria and diseases	
TSH outside age-specific reference ranges, thyroid diseases 0-17 years: reference ranges Kratzsch et al. 2008 ¹ 18 years: reference ranges Surup et al. 2021 ² >19 years: reference ranges elecsys TSH ³	
CRP $\geq$ 20 mg/L	CRP $\geq$ 20 mg/L Leukocytes $\geq$ 11 x 10 ⁹ /L
Renal diseases	History of renal insufficiency, Current treatment or history of dialysis
Liver diseases	History of liver cirrhosis, Current treatment or history of hepatitis during last 12 months
Epilepsy	Current treatment or history of epilepsy during last 12 months
Previous history of digestive diseases	History of chronic inflammatory bowel disease, Current medication for chronic ulcers
Heart disease	Current treatment or history of heart insufficiency during last 12 months, history of cardiac infarction during last 12 months, Current treatment or history of stroke during last 12 months
History of cancer	Cancer and cancer treatment during last 12 months, cancer in non-remission
Type 1 / Type 2 diabetes mellitus	Type 1 / Type 2 diabetes mellitus, gestational diabetes or diabetes after pancreatitis
Height SDS $\leq$ -2, Weight SDS $\leq$ -2	History of growth hormone deficiency/acromegaly, oligo- or amenorrhea or other endocrine disease, muscle diseases
Preterm child if $\leq$ 2 years of age, suspect neonatal screening	Current treatment or history of Parkinson's Disease
Diseases concerning muscle, coagulation, angiology, depression, addiction, other diseases	History of HIV, Current treatment or history of MS, Current treatment of tuberculosis, varicella, shingles, measles, rubella, sepsis, STD (sexual transmitted disease), COPD
(B.2) Medication	
Biotin: assay-interfering-agent	

Glucocorticoid medication (systemic, inhalative and non-inhalative topic)
 Systemic anabolics and antianemics,
 Medication for digestive diseases
 Pancreatic hormones, parathyroid medication
 Systemic antibiotics
 Antineoplastic and immunomodulatory medication
 Antiepileptics, antiparkinsonian medication
 Inhibitors of prolactin, androgens, ovulation releasing drugs, antiandrogens, modulators of genital system, emergency contraception, alpha-adrenoreceptor antagonists, 36estosterone-5-alpha-reductase inhibitors
 Hypophysial and hypothalamic hormone medication, thyroid medication, hypophysial function testing

Chlormadinone	Chlormadinone at age <40 years without estrogen treatment
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Antidiabetic medication, insulin treatment	Insulin treatment
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Heart therapy, antihypertensive treatment, diuretics, peripheral vasodilators, vasoprotectors, medication affecting the RAAS	/
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Psycholeptics, psychoanaleptics	/
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Adolescent girls - sexual hormone medication - ATC-Codes

CD (Contraceptive drugs)
 G03AA, G03AB

Adult females - sexual hormone medication ATC-Codes

CD (Contraceptive drugs)
 G03AA, G03AB, G03AC, G03AD, ATC

HRT (Hormone replacement therapy)
 G03C, G03D, G03F

Medication classification is based on ATC Codes and documented application route for LIFE Child and LIFE Adult derives from interview.

Medication classification is based on ATC Codes and documented application route for LIFE Child and LIFE Adult derives from interview. For the other cohorts, we estimated the classification using the compound's name, which came from an interview with the BRC cohort (in some cases with dosage) and from self-reports in the student cohort.

References

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